

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AS A PURPOSEFUL SYSTEM OF EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the primary factors of study room management, it discusses the dreams and objectives, features and sorts of school room management.

Key words: class teacher, student, educational institution, class team, task, significant creative activity, educational process successful socialization

Introduction: Education is one of the most important components of education in the interests of a person, society, and the state. The foremost obligations of training are: the formation of students' civic obligation and criminal self-awareness, spirituality and culture, initiative, independence, tolerance and the capacity to effectively socialize in society. Educational functions in a general education institution are performed by all teaching staff. However, the key role in solving the problems of education belongs to the teacher, who is entrusted with the functions of a class teacher.

What is class leadership? What is its main purpose? What are its features, tasks, functions, forms of work, let's try to figure it out.

“True love is born only in a heart that has experienced the fate of another person. How important it is for children to have a friend who needs to be taken care of, ” this statement belongs to the great Soviet innovative teacher Vasily Aleksandrovich Sukhomlinsky, which can be fully attributed to the activities of the class teacher.

There are many different points of view on the definition of the concept of "class teacher", let's consider some of them.

In the pedagogical dictionary edited by G. M. Kodzhaspirov, a *class teacher* is a teacher whose job responsibilities include: promoting the creation of favorable conditions for the individual development and formation of the child's personality; making the necessary adjustments to the system of his education; assistance in solving problems that arise in children when communicating with each other, with teachers, parents; organization and education of the class team.

The following definition is given in Rozhkov's manual "For the elegance trainer": a *class teacher* is a faculty instructor who plays the features of an organizer of kid's life, a corrector of interpersonal family members and a protector of scholars of his magnificence in hard enterprise and mental collisions of faculty life.

And the final definition, the office has become a key one on the World Wide Web, the *class teacher* is the leader of the group, the bearer of culture, the organizer and participant in the collective creative activity of children, the inspirer, guardian and friend of his pupils

The purpose of the classroom management - to create conditions for self-development and self-realization of the student's personality, his successful socialization in society.

What are the tasks of the class teacher? *The tasks of the class teacher include nine main components, including:*

1. Formation and development of the class team
2. Creation of favorable psychological and pedagogical conditions for personal development, self-affirmation of each student, preservation of originality and disclosure of his potential abilities.
3. Formation of a healthy lifestyle
4. Organization of the system of relations through various forms of educational activity of the class team.
5. Protection of the rights and interests of students.

6. Organization of systematic work with students in the classroom.
7. Humanization of relations between students, between students and teaching staff
8. Formation of students' moral meanings and spiritual guidelines.
9. Organization of socially significant creative activity of students.

What are the functions of a class teacher?

The tasks of the class teacher is a purposeful, systematic, planned process, built on the basis of the charter of the educational institution, other local acts, analysis of previous activities, positive and negative trends in social life, a personality-oriented approach to students, taking into account the urgent tasks facing the teaching staff of the educational institution, and situations in the collective class, interethnic and interfaith relations. For a pedagogically competent, successful and effective performance of their functions, the class teacher needs to know well the psychological and pedagogical foundations of working with children of a particular age, be informed about the latest trends, methods and forms of educational activities, and master modern technologies of education.

Functions of the class teacher:

1. Organizational and coordinating:

- making sure verbal exchange among the instructional organization and the family;
- establishing contacts with parents of college students, helping them in teaching college students (personally, through psychologist, social pedagogue, extra schooling teacher);
- preserving consultations, conversations with parents of college students;
- interplay with coaching team of workers, in addition to with academic and help personnel of the academic organization;

- organization in the classroom of an educational process that is optimal for the development of the positive potential of the personality of students within the framework of the activities of the general school team;

- organization of educational work with students through the holding of "small teachers' councils", pedagogical councils, thematic and other events;

- stimulating and taking into account the various activities of students, including in the system of additional education for children;

- interplay with every scholar and the elegance crew as a whole;

- maintaining documentation (magnificence journal, non-public documents of college students)

2. Communicative:

- law of interpersonal members of the family among college students;

- establishing interplay among coaching workforce and college students;

- promoting a general favorable psychological climate in the class team

- assisting students in the formation of communicative qualities.

3. Analytical and prognostic:

- have a look at of the character traits of college students and the dynamics in their improvement;

- determining the nation and improvement possibilities of the magnificence crew.

4. Control:

- monitoring the development of every scholar;

- monitoring the attendance of education periods through college students.

As for the practical significance of class leadership, then, in my opinion, everything is extremely simple here. Based on my own leadership experience, although not great, I can say the following: being a class teacher is not easy, but at the same time very interesting and exciting, because you perform many different roles at once: mentor, parent, friend, teacher, friend, assistant, etc. The most important thing, of course, is sincerity and love for your pupils, because they feel you and your attitude towards them. For me personally, class leadership is the most incredible and unique feeling that is worth fighting for and improving, because the love of your cool team is worth more than any award. Therefore, I believe that class leadership is one of the main goals of the school system of education

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